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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the preliminary outcomes of the monitoring strategy for the StandICT.eu 2026 FOREST (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards) group, covering the first half of the project period from January 2023 to June 2024.

The document provides an overview of the activities conducted as part of FOREST and includes a detailed description of the forum and its objectives. Additionally, it lists all active FOREST members, detailing their roles and areas of expertise. This forum includes experts in standardisation strategy and development. Each member's diverse backgrounds and experiences contribute to this FORUM's robust structure and effective functioning.

A key objective of FOREST is to monitor sensitive issues related to standardisation. Therefore, this report also provides a detailed update on FOREST's progress in two primary areas, which were selected as a focus in this reporting period in agreement with the European Commission (EC). These topics refer to 1) women's involvement in ICT standardisation and 2) the consideration of human rights in standards development.

The report also outlines the following steps and future actions planned to fully achieve FOREST's objectives in the second half of the project.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	AI Act
AUWP	Annual Union Work Programme
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
EC	European Commission
ESO	European Standards Organisations
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FOREST	Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards
HR	Human Rights
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE SA	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
NSB	National Standards Bodies
OC	Open Calls
OHCHR	Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights
R&D	Research & Development
SBS	Small Business Standards
SC	Standards Committee
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
TC	Technical Committee
TSAG	Telecommunication Standardisation Advisory Group
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WTSA	World Telecommunication Standardisation Assembly

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is a direct output of the project deliverable D6.3 “FOREST” submitted as part of the evaluation of the FOREST group.

Initially, when the current StandICT.eu 2026 project proposal was awarded funding back in 2022, FOREST was conceived to be a body primarily focussed on providing policy recommendations to the EC regarding ICT standardisation.

However, early in the project, following the kick-off meeting in February 2023 and the official establishment of the High-Level Forum on EU Standardisation, it became evident that FOREST’s objectives needed to shift to avoid overlaps with key existing initiatives. In particular when it came to the development of policy insights and recommendations, this reorientation took several months to be agreed upon and formalised. An initial meeting of FOREST was held in March 2023 (M03) as per the original Grant Agreement timeline. Initially, these meetings were reserved for consortium members and the European Commission to discuss priorities and evolving needs, as opposed to the broader FOREST group.

While the initial deliverable for this task, D6.3 was initially meant to develop a methodology for policy recommendations in anticipation of future policy-related deliverables, the project has currently successfully completed the reorientation exercise. This has required the opening of a formal request for amendment of the grant agreement. A second meeting, in the form of the official kick-off open to external members, as described in section 2, took place in May 2024.

At the time of writing, the consortium is finalising the amendment to the Grant Agreement needed to formalise FOREST’s evolution. This amendment will transform FOREST into a body dedicated to raising awareness and sparking interest around sensitive issues that require further investigation or that address challenges and concerns contrary to EU values. Details on the new FOREST’s missions and objectives are reported in section 2 of this deliverable.

As a consequence, the present deliverable, D6.4, and the forthcoming D6.5, will reflect this new direction. These documents will report on the project’s sensitisation efforts regarding critical topics. One such focus is the role of women in ICT standards, with two dedicated events held in 2023 and 2024. Another focus is the intersection of human rights and ICT standardisation, highlighted by an event organised in June 2024. Further details are reported in sections 3 and 4 of this document.

The two topics of “women’s role in ICT standardisation” and “human rights in ICT standardisation” are critical for several reasons. Women’s involvement in ICT standardisation ensures diverse perspectives and inclusive standards that better serve all segments of society. This inclusivity helps prevent biases and gaps that might emerge if only a homogenous group were involved. Moreover, promoting women’s participation in ICT standardisation contributes to gender equality in the ICT industry more broadly, empowering women and encouraging their continued involvement in technical fields. This not only enriches the standardisation process but also drives innovation and competitiveness by tapping into a wider pool of talent and ideas. Furthermore, considering that there is a shortage of experts who are skilled standardisation professionals it is imperative to attract

individuals from diverse backgrounds and fields, gaining a richer understanding of sustainability within the standardisation process. This wider perspective is key to crafting effective and inclusive regulations that will support sustainable future goals and widen the standardisation talent pool to draw from.

Human rights considerations in ICT standardisation are equally crucial. Ensuring that standards uphold and protect fundamental rights fosters trust in technology and its applications. Standards incorporating human rights principles help safeguard against abuses and ensure that technologies are developed and implemented ethically. This is particularly important as ICT becomes increasingly pervasive in everyday life, impacting everything from privacy and security to freedom of expression and access to information.

In addition to these activities, project partners involved in FOREST are responsible for compiling a confidential early warnings report, accessible only to the European Commission and project partners after every two Open Calls (OCs). The first report, covering OC1 and OC2, was delivered in early May 2024. It highlights topics of concern submitted by StandICT fellows for the EC's further consideration.

By identifying and addressing these sensitive issues, FOREST aims to promote a more inclusive and ethical approach to ICT standardisation, aligning with EU values and enhancing the EU's leadership in this crucial area.

2. FORUM ON EUROPEAN STRATEGY FOR ICT STANDARDS (FOREST)

2.1 Mission and Objectives

FOREST is the StandICT.eu body ensuring that the resources of experts are well-supervised to match the European Commission's objectives by liaising with the Technical Committee (TC) and Standards Committee (SC) chairs or Working (WG) conveners. This will facilitate the identification of sectors and domains where enhanced engagement from EU and Associated countries might be beneficial. Furthermore, the diverse backgrounds of its members will help increase EU leadership in international standards activities.

Additionally, FOREST seeks to foster collaborations with other EU-funded initiatives focused on standardisation. This strategic approach not only aims to contribute to the promotion of standards documents like the Code of Practice but also aspires to cultivate a community dedicated to ICT Standardisation and strategy expertise,

As a consequence, FOREST's main objectives are:

- Monitoring sensitive issues identified through the StandICT.eu fellows;
- Identifying recognised standardisation experts to be invited to StandICT.eu events dedicated to the selected sensitive issues;
- Supporting the development of synergies with other initiatives and projects (HSBooster, Blockstand, INSTAR, etc.) around the identified sensitive topics.

It is important to notice that these main objectives have been updated after the grant agreement amendment.

2.2 Membership

FOREST is made up of senior experts from European Standards Organisations (ESOs), international stakeholders, National Standards Bodies (NSBs) of EU Member States, and Open Source organisations.

Currently, 8 active members constitute this expert group, all with different backgrounds and areas of expertise related to the project goals. The group meets virtually every quarter, considering its geographical distribution. The chair of the FOREST is Dave Lewis, an Associate Professor at the School of Computer Science and Statistics at Trinity College Dublin and the head of its Artificial Intelligence Discipline who is currently active in international standardisation of Trustworthy AI at ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42.

For a better understanding, the following table presents information about the experts:

Name	Affiliation	Qualifications
Christian Grafenauer	AI Expert in CEN/CENELEC JTC 21	Specialist in Blockchain, ISO/CEN Standardisation, Privacy (GDPR), Anonymisation, AI and Cybersecurity.
Dave Lewis	TCD	From ADAPT Centre in Trinity College Dublin. Participates in the NSAI mirror committee on AI and its ICT coordination committee.
Diana Soeiro	Portuguese Business Ethics Association (APEE)	Scientific Research & Consulting for Sustainable Cities and Communities, emphasising Management Systems & Governance, Smart Cities, Artificial Intelligence and Wellbeing. Standardisation involvement: IPQ/CT 224 Expert; IPQ/CT224-WG1 Management Systems Chair; CEN 465 Delegate; CEN 465-WG1 Nature-Based Solutions Expert; ISO 268 Delegate; ISO 268-WG1 Management Systems Expert (HoD).
Lindsay Frost	Freelance Author & Consultant	The chairman of the new ETSI Industry Specification Group for cross-cutting Context Information Management (ETSI ISG CIM) aims to consult stakeholders, especially from the areas of semantic interoperability and Smart City domains, and find a consensus on how to publish and subscribe to information from various sources (IoT, existing city databases, web, and mobile apps).
Panos Kudumakis	Standardisation Expert	Specialist in Digital Media Standards, Technology, Policy and Strategy. Head of UK Delegation to ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 (aka MPEG & JPEG), Chair of UK national mirror committee to ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 and Chair of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG3 Subgroup on Smart

		Contracts for Media. Expert of ISO/IEC JTC1 in AI, Web3, Metaverse, Smart Cities, e-Government and Sustainability.
Philip Maurer	CEN/CENELEC	Project Manager for RTD Collaboration at the CEN & CENELEC Management Centre in Brussels. Linking standards to academics & researchers, participating in a range of HE projects: InDiCo-Global, RISERS, STAN4SWAP & EDU4Standards.eu
Sandra Feliciano	Polytechnic Institute of Porto	Invited Adjunct Professor at Porto Polytechnic and Head of Research Engagement for AI & Cybersecurity at MENAPS. Standardisation memberships on ICT currently are IPQ/CT 163 & 223, CEN/TC 353, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, 36 & 42.
Viveka Bonde	ISO/IEC	Swedish lawyer. Has been working with AI & ethics in ISO, SC42 since 2019. Was the PE of ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG 3 TR 24368 'AI -overview of ethical and societal concerns'. PE of the current SC 42 Project, TS 22443 AI - guidance on societal concerns and ethical considerations. Also Active in CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG4.

3. INITIATIVES FOR THE INVOLVEMENT OF WOMEN IN ICT STANDARDISATION

As clarified in the previous section, one of FOREST's main objectives is monitoring sensitive topics in standardisation. Therefore, working on initiatives involving women in ICT standardisation is imperative. Having women participate in standardisation initiatives can lead to more inclusive and effective standards because the process ensures that a broader range of experiences and needs are considered.

3.1 Webinars on Women in ICT Standardisation

A series of two webinars explicitly targeted to women were conducted, continuing the success of the first webinar dedicated to the same topic organised in 2022 under the remit of StandICT.eu 2023.

3.1.1 WOMEN IN ICT STANDARDISATION, SECOND EDITION

[The second webinar of "Women in ICT Standardisation"](#) (with the first one being the one organised by StandICT.eu 2023) took place on the 4th of July 2023 to discuss the current status of women's participation and contribution to standards and technical committees and activities in the ICT domain. Given FOREST's objective to synergies with other EU-funded projects on these topics, the webinar was organised in collaboration with [HSBooster.eu](#) and [STAND4EU](#).

The webinar highlights the gender gap in ICT standardisation and discusses the gender dimension in standards. Representatives from leading European and International Standards Developing Organisations were invited to share their expertise and experiences in promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in ICT standardisation and their contributions to standards development in various ICT technological domains.

The event featured the following list of speakers:

- Silvana Muscella - Trust-IT Services CEO & StandICT.eu 2026 Coordinator
- Raquel Fernández Horcajada - Research Programme Manager at REA (European Commission)
- Maitane Olabarria Uzquiano - Secretary General at Small Business Standards (SBS)
- Viveka Bonde - Advokat, ISO Project Editor & StandICT.eu fellow
- Ivana Mijatovic - Full Professor at the University of Belgrade & StandICT.eu Standards Academy chair

- Judith E. Y. Rossebø - Cybersecurity specialist at ABB AS & CLC/TC 65X
- Olga Meyer - Research and Development Group Lead at Fraunhofer IPA & Stand4EU representative
- Emilia Tantar - Chief Data and Artificial Intelligence Officer at Black Swan LUX & StanICT.eu fellow

The webinar aimed to:

- Discuss the current status of women's participation and contribution to Standards & Technical committees and activities in the ICT domain.
- Highlight the achievements and current activities of various European and International Standards Developing Organisations in promoting diversity, equity and inclusion in the field.
- Discuss the role of women in developing standards in the respective ICT technological domains.
- Encourage more women to be active in the field of ICT Standardisation.

The discussions emphasised mentorship and networking opportunities for women in this field, showcasing how these resources empower them. The webinar explored successful initiatives and best practices that effectively promote women's active participation in standardisation. The webinar was divided into different sessions following the expertise domain of each speaker. A summary of each one is provided below:

- Session 1, "EU policy (for inclusive) gender equality" by Raquel Fernandez Horcajada, focussed on how the limited participation of women is detrimental to the development of standards. She addressed the critical question of how the low involvement of women results from individual preference or systemic obstacles. She found that stereotypes and a lack of digital confidence are the main obstacles. Furthermore, she talked about the Commission for Equality, policies to increase gender diversity and the European Gender Equality Strategy.
- Session 2, "Advancing inclusivity - The SME experience" by Maitane Olabarria, focussed mainly on the Small Business Standards (SBS) experience, explaining what it is and its objectives, providing improvement statistics and explaining current projects and initiatives. Three main future actions were identified: raising awareness, training, and monitoring progress,
- Session 3, by Viveka Bonde, introduced the activities carried out by SC 42, which deals with AI standardisation. Additionally, she worked on an overview of ethical and societal concerns. She talked about her experience as a woman working in standardisation, advocating for various experts from interdisciplinary backgrounds. She explained the ISO IEC Code of Conduct.
- Session 4, by Ivana Mijatovic, discussed the need to challenge gender stereotypes. It shared the results of a survey about the role of standards

in overcoming gender prejudice and how it wants to bring standardisation closer to women leaders, researchers, and entrepreneurs by providing more training and education for future women.

- Session 5, “Cyber Security Standardisation,” was delivered by Judith E. Y. Rossebo. In it, she shared her experiences and journey working on standardisation, aiming to inspire other women to start working on standardisation.
- Session 6 by Olga Meyer described the Stand4eu project and its phases.
- Session 7, “A journey in standardisation from an SME R&D lens” Emilia Tantar shared her experiences and projects she has worked on.

Women in ICT Standards #2

WEBINAR

SPEAKERS

- Raquel Fernández Horcajada**
Research Programme Manager at REA (European Commission)
- Silvana Muscella**
Trust-IT Services CEO & StandICT.eu 2026 Coordinator
- Maitane Olabarria Uzquiano**
Secretary General at Small Business Standards (SBS)
- Viveka Bonde**
Advokat, ISO Project Editor & StandICT.eu Fellow
- Ivana Mijatovic**
Full Professor at University of Belgrade & StandICT.eu Standards Academy chair
- Judith E. Y. Rossebo**
Cybersecurity specialist at ABB AS & CLC/TC 65X
- Olga Meyer**
Research and Development Group Lead at Fraunhofer IPA & Stand4EU representative
- Emilia Tantar**
Chief Data and Artificial Intelligence Officer at Black Swan LUX & StandICT.eu Fellow

04th July
10:30 - 12:00 (CEST)

standICT.eu 2026 in collaboration with Hsbooster.eu and STAND4EU. Funded by the European Union.

Figure 1 - Women in ICT Standards (July 2023)

Some highlights from the event are available in the [post-event webinar report published on StandICT.eu Zenodo channel](#)

3.1.2 WOMEN IN ICT STANDARDISATION, THIRD EDITION

[The third Webinar of “Women in ICT Standardisation” took place on March 7, 2024.](#) with the purpose of bringing together leading voices in the field of European standardisation. The webinar was organised in collaboration with five other EU-funded projects dedicated to advancing European

standardisation activities: [HSBooster.eu](https://www.hsbooster.eu), [SEEBLOCKS.eu](https://www.seeblocks.eu), [EDU4Standards.eu](https://www.edu4standards.eu), [STAND4EU](https://www.stand4eu.eu), and [BLOCKSTAND](https://www.blockstand.eu).

The main objective of the webinar was to discuss and highlight the critical gender gaps in ICT standardisation, with a particular focus on the 8 policy priorities identified by the European Commission (EC) in the Annual Union Work Programme (AUWP) for European standardisation:

- Technologies for European high-performance computing and European quantum communication infrastructure;
- Critical Raw Materials (CRM) - Recycling Of Permanent magnets and exploration, extraction, refining and recycling of CRM
- EU Trusted Data Framework;
- European Digital Identity Framework;
- Eco-design of air-to-air conditioning and heat pumps;
- Cybersecurity Requirements;
- Hydrogen technologies and components;
- Electric Vehicles Charging Infrastructure

The event featured the following list of speakers:

- Eszter Batta - Policy Officer, European Commission, DG GROW
- Silvana Muscella - Trust-IT Services CEO & StandICT.eu 2026 Coordinator - Event Moderator
- Rim Belhassine-Cherif, PhD - Chair of Network of Women in ITU-T
- Barbara Reiter (University of Graz, EDU4Standards)
- Isabella De Michelis CEO & Founder at ErnieApp Ltd & IEC JTC SC35 WG4 (ISO, Stand4EU)
- Paola Sabatelli Amato - (HSbooster.eu & StandICT.eu)
- Lluïsa Marsal Llacuna - Intelligenter, (ISO CEN-Cenelec, IEC, ITU-T, BlockStand.eu)
- Sudha Iyer - CITI & SEEBLOCKS.eu
- Sandra Feliciano - Head of Research Engagement - AI & Cybersecurity at MENAPS (ISO, IPQ, CEN-CENELEC, HSbooster.eu)
- Marzia Bolpagni - Associate Director at Mace (ISO, CEN-CENELEC, UNI)
- Paloma Llana - eIDAS and eID Scheme Manager, CerteIDAS (CEN, ETSI, ISO, IEC)

The webinar analysed the main obstacles in ICT Standardisation while providing an engaged audience to showcase avenues women can take to achieve success in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). In particular, the webinar aimed to:

- Analyse the main obstacles and problems that persist in ICT standardisation;

- Discuss and analyse the main results and achievements obtained at the European and International levels in promoting equity and inclusion in this field;
- Provide examples of practices and experiences empowering the role of women in standards development organisations and technical committees in the ICT domains;
- Give a general overview of the leading gender gaps in the 8 policy priorities identified under the AUWP.

Inclusion and diversity in standardisation processes are crucial. Addressing gender issues and providing equal opportunities for women in ICT standardisation is essential for creating a more balanced and representative industry.

#3 WOMEN in ICT Standardisation

WEBINAR
7th March
10:30 - 12:15 (CET)

SPEAKERS

- Silvana Muscella**
Trust-IT Services CEO & StandICT.eu 2026 Coordinator
- Eszter Batta**
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG GROW
- Rim Belhassine-Cherif**
Chair of Network of Women in ITU-T
- Barbara Reiter**
Lecturer at Karl-Franzens-Universität, Graz | EDU4Standards
- Isabella De Michelis**
CEO & Founder at ErnieApp Ltd & IEC JTC SC35 WG4 | Stand4EU
- Paola Amato**
Eu policy and Funding expert. Independent standardisation expert
- Lluïsa Marsal Llacuna**
Intelligenter & ISO, CEN-Cenelec, IEC | BlockStand.eu
- Sudha Iyer**
CITI & SEEBLOCKS.eu
- Sandra Feliciano**
MENAPS, AESTAS INSIGNIS, IPO, CEN-CENELEC and ISO | HSbooster.EU
- Marzia Bolpagni**
Head of BIM International - Associate Director at Mace ISO, CEN & UNI
- Paloma Llana**
eIDAS and eID Scheme Manager at CertelDAS & CEN, ETSI, ISO, IEC

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Figure 2 - Women in ICT Standardisation (March 2024)

Further details are available in the [post-event webinar report published on StandICT.eu Zenodo channel](#)

3.2 Outcomes from Webinars

This series of events focused on women in ICT and included 18 experts/speakers and 112 attendees who participated live. The attendees were distributed as follows:

Webinar	Registered Men	Registered Women	Total registration	Attendees
Women in ICT Standardisation, Second Edition	25	56	81	60
Women in ICT Standardisation, Third Edition	20	61	81	52
Total	45	117	162	112

These webinars addressed the current state of female representation and challenges in ICT standardisation, from the role standards can play in supporting gender equality, adopting a gender lens when drafting standards, and identifying gender gaps to mentorship and networking opportunities.

While progress has been made, further work is necessary. Encouraging women to participate in ICT Standardisation is crucial to reducing the gender gap and achieving standards that benefit us all. However, a deep understanding of the many layers of the problem is needed and the analyses of women's representation on standardisation technical committees are complex to analyse, as there are significant differences between:

- being nominated as delegates/experts
- travelling to and attending meetings
- actively participating in meetings
- being heard and taken seriously during meetings
- embracing leading roles (convenor, secretary, chair)

There is a need for careful individual consideration of each of these aspects and there are challenges to the collection of reliable data to enable solid and useful conclusions for designing effective measures. It requires a deep dive inside the “black box” of standardisation, as some data can only be collected through direct observation during meetings – participant observation being probably the best research method to apply in these cases.

4. HUMAN RIGHTS IN ICT STANDARDISATION

Human rights, enshrined in conventions, declarations, and other legal texts, form the bedrock upon which all societal activities must align. This principle of course extends to ICT standardisation, where technical decisions should be scrutinised for their impact on human rights. These decisions, once embedded in business processes, affect users, suppliers, and citizens globally. FOREST is dedicated to exploring these concerns and addressing them effectively.

4.1 Webinar on Human Rights and ICT Standardisation

On Thursday, June 6th, 2024, StandICT.eu 2026, in collaboration with the HSBooster.eu project, organised a [webinar](#) dedicated to discussing amongst experts working on human rights and standards how to ensure Human Rights (HR) are considered and dealt with when addressing technical specifications in ICT standardisation.

The motivation behind the webinar was to provide background and increase support among like-minded and other third countries for looking into what is needed to integrate HR in the ICT standards development process.

The experts shared how their work addresses human rights concerns in emerging technologies such as Virtual worlds, Data, cybersecurity, IoT, AI, telemedicine, and more.

The event featured the following list of speakers:

- Silvana Muscella, StandICT.eu Project Coordinator
- Emilio Davila Gonzalez, Head of ICT Standardisation Sector, DG CONNECT, European Commission
- Jochen Friedrich, Member of the ETSI Board, IBM
- Olivier Alais, ITU
- Arnaud Taddei, Broadcom and ITU
- Nicholas Ferguson, HSbooster.eu Project Coordinator
- Invited panellists:
 - Viveka Bonde, Partner, Bonde Advokate, ISO (StandICT.eu Fellow)
 - Christian Grafenauer, ISO & CEN-CENELEC (StandICT.eu Fellow)
 - Shakira Bedoya, Senior Compliance Officer, Danske Bank, ISO (StandICT.eu & Seeblocks Fellow and HSbooster.eu expert)
 - Maria Grazia Porcedda, Assistant Professor, Trinity College Dublin
 - Veronique Lerch, Independent Human Rights Consultant
 - Gabriela Garham, ISO, General Manager at ADIMECH AG

- Monica Martinez Vargas, Executive Director of Strategy 2 Succeed
- Charles Kiser Webb, Senior Information Technology Executive

Figure 3 - Human Rights & ICT Standardisation (June 2024)

4.2 Outcomes from Webinar

The preliminary recommendations derived from the discussions at the workshop are summarised below.

4.2.1 Policy Commitment

- If standards do not comply with, they may not be applicable within the EU which is not what is wanted or needed.
- Human Rights issues should consider all stakeholder interests such as commercial- business interests, interoperability that should all coexist together.
- The Human Rights Council in 2021 with Res 47/23 called for closer cooperation between OHCHR and SDOs including ITU to consider the relation btw human rights and technical standards.
- The AI Act will really push for this. Recital 121 AIA says: A balanced representation of interests involving all relevant stakeholders in the development of standards, in particular SMEs, consumer organisations and environmental and social stakeholders are necessary in

accordance with Articles 5 and 6 of Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 should therefore be encouraged.

4.2.2 Technical

- Standards enable tech advancement on a global scale as cost-effectively as possible.
- ITU urges to establish a clear link between technical concepts and human rights. We still need to translate human rights into technical terms and to embed human rights into technical standards. ITU-T focus groups are open to all parties.
- It is reasonable to bring human rights “by-design” in standardisation. A lot seems to be high-level vision though, without execution in mind. “Vision without execution is the definition of an hallucination!” Lessons learned show that a lot of conditions are not in place.
- There are multiple technical standards out there, but it's the market that decides the winning standard. It's up to the designers to tailor the standards taking into account ethics and human rights.

4.2.3 Societal

- Bring human rights experts, in particular those with tech knowledge, into standardisation activities, to bridge the gap.
- Lack of transparency in the process largely due to standards being behind paywalls, there now from March 2024 this is now overridden.
- Sustainable Fintech to support SDGs & engage with other Fintech experts.
- “Good ethics is good business.” Implementation of standards supporting human rights (privacy, security, safety, quality of life) is good for the bottom line, avoiding financial, legal, and reputational damage.
- Promote standardisation, to a point where the public recognize a “flag / stamp”, and see value on that.
- ACTION: Call for successful examples & best practices of HR considerations into ICT standards StandICT.eu, HSBooster.eu & within the various SDO committees.

Following the delivery of the workshop, the participating experts have worked on a detailed post-event report to dive deeper into the topics discussed and elaborate further recommendations for different stakeholders. At the moment of submitting this deliverable, the report is in the finalisation stage and will be made publicly available at the beginning of July. This report will also be distributed to StandICT.eu funded fellows as an instrument to reflect on the raised issues and try and implement some of the recommendations in their daily standardisation work.

4.3 Additional Approaches

This section explores complementary approaches that relate to the main goals and should therefore be considered during the development of the project.

4.3.1 ISO CODE OF ETHICS AND CONDUCT

The International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) brings together experts from different countries and sectors to develop international standards through a fair, transparent, and consensus-based process that considers the needs of all stakeholders. ISO aims to create solutions that benefit the entire global community, not just individual organisations or people. Because of this, ISO has a strict code of conduct that its members must follow, ensuring the organisation's work is ethical and trustworthy.

The set of principles they adhere to are (ISO Code of Ethics and Conduct, 2023):

1. Comply with legal and statutory obligations
2. Perform and act in good faith, consistent with the purpose, policies and principles of the organisation
3. Behave ethically
4. Promote and enable all voices to be heard
5. Engage constructively in ISO activities
6. Declare actual and potential conflicts of interest and manage them appropriately
7. Protect confidential information
8. Protect ISO assets
9. Avoid and prevent any form of bribery or corruption
10. Escalate and resolve disputes and uphold the agreed resolution

4.3.2 SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS BY UN

Launched in 2015 by all UN member countries, the 2030 Agenda is a global plan for a sustainable future. It centres around 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that require all nations to work together (UN, 2015). From reducing social inequalities and building a sustainable economy to combating climate change, the SDGs represent a comprehensive approach for a better future. The key to achieving these goals is collaboration between all stakeholders, from governments to private businesses. They must work together and leverage every available resource to realise this vision.

Turning grand goals into real-world progress is complex, so standards become crucial. Voluntary and consensus-based standards can establish clear and shared guidelines, promote the spread of best practices and innovative solutions, and allow organisations and countries to meet the SDGs.

Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that two ISO standardisation initiatives support the adoption of these goals.

- [ISO 53001](#) Management Systems for UN Sustainable development goals – Requirements. Outlines what an organisation needs to do to set up a Sustainable Development Goals Management System which is required when organisations need to demonstrate and enhance its work and performance towards the UN SDGs, or to manage responsibilities in a systematic manner that contributes to the pillars of sustainability. This will allow organisations to enhance their performance, fulfil compliance obligations, achieve selected SDG objectives, increase success and create trust and confidence in relevant existing and future stakeholders (ISO n.d. -b). This standard is under development, being at the Working Draft (WD) stage by the time of closing this report.
- [IWA 48](#) Framework for Implementing Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Principles (Under development) (ISO n.d. -c). This standardisation deliverable is under development, and has its publication planned for the last quarter of 2024.

4.3.3 GENDER AND STANDARDISATION

To further support the main goal of the project which aims to monitor sensitive issues related to standards, it is important to consider standardisation initiatives addressing gender issues.

- [ISO 53800](#) Guidelines for the promotion and implementation of gender equality and women's empowerment: Provides guidelines for organisations to promote and implement gender equality and women's empowerment, focusing on overcoming the inequality arising from gender-specific roles and is applicable to all organisations, regardless of their size, location, or field of activity (ISO, 2024).
- [ISO 45010](#) Menstruation, menstrual health and menopause in the workplace — Guidance: Provides guidance on developing policies and practices that are supportive of the menstruation, menstrual health and peri/menopause experiences of employees in the workplace (ISO n.d. -a). This standard is based on BS 30416, a British standard with the same scope, and is currently under further development to reach international consensus at ISO. It is at the Working Draft (WD) stage by the time of closing this report.

5. NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSIONS

As we move forward with the updated roles and tasks of FOREST, the insights gained from this phase of the project will significantly shape the remaining activities under Task 6.3. The reorientation of FOREST, from a body primarily focused on the formulation of policy recommendations to one dedicated to raising awareness around sensitive issues, has provided valuable lessons on the evolving needs and priorities within the landscape of ICT standardisation. The main learnings are summarised as follows:

- The shift to addressing sensitive issues such as women’s involvement in ICT standardisation and human rights considerations has underscored the importance of inclusivity and ethical standards in ICT. This realignment allows FOREST to fill gaps that other initiatives have not addressed.
- The initial phases highlighted the need to engage diverse stakeholders, including external experts, on the identified topics.
- The discussion of the identified issues in the form of online events has proven effective in raising awareness and fostering dialogue. These events have also highlighted the need for continuous engagement and follow-up to maintain momentum and drive change.

Moving forward, we will leverage these insights to enhance our activities, ensuring they are impactful and aligned with FOREST’s revised objectives. As mentioned in section 4.2, a detailed post-event report in cooperation with HSbooster will be released in the coming days to highlight the main insights and recommendations related to the HR event. FOREST will organise follow-up events in cooperation with other EU projects on these or additional equally sensitive topics in the following months. The definition of the topics will be agreed upon by FOREST members and the EC, and the results will be included in the updated version of this deliverable due in M36.

6. REFERENCES

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